

Adaptive and Scalable Multi-Mobile-Robot Simulation

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Abstract—A simulation framework is introduced based on ROS and NVIDIA’s Isaac Sim to create a scalable, adaptable Industry 4.0 virtual laboratory for the integration and testing of 3D Digital Twin production assets and interactions with multi-robot systems in complex environments. With features like scene generation, virtual sensor definition and interoperable data collection, the pipeline enables research in algorithm design, AI, and human-robot collaboration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The safe integration of autonomous mobile systems such as handling robots, transport systems and cobots into industrial settings is still a challenging task. Beside harsh environmental conditions with dust, dirt, noise and high temperatures, new requirements arise under variable production scenarios, in which the process sequences, the number and kind of active elements (robots, human workers) as well the position of production equipment and routes are dynamically changing. Task planning and robot action must be adopted accordingly efficiently. Therefore new simulation-based adaptation and learning approaches are in favor for such scenarios. Recent robot navigation research utilizing Robot Operating System (ROS), Isaac Sim, and scene randomization emphasizes enhanced adaptability and performance in dynamic environments. A deep reinforcement learning (DRL) approach for improved navigation accuracy, is demonstrated in a ROS2-based DRL navigation stack [1]. Photorealistic simulations in NVIDIA Isaac Sim support the development of robust navigation systems, while realistic environment interactions, such as navigating movable obstacles, can be investigated [2]. For higher robustness and generalization in dynamically altering environments, scene randomization techniques can be utilized [3]. The ability to randomize production layouts and robot interactions enables the testing of adaptive control strategies in modular production, where unpredictable task sequences and dynamic object placements are common.

The pipeline presented here combines ROS2 for modular robot control and NVIDIA’s Isaac Sim for high-fidelity physics based simulation. This work focuses on architectural details and highlights the potential of the pipeline. Unlike existing simulation frameworks, this pipeline specifically addresses the challenges of flexible, modular production systems by integrating advanced scene randomization, digital twin synchronization, and scalable multi-robot experimentation.

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II. SIMULATION PIPELINE ARCHITECTURE

The simulation pipeline works as a standalone Python application using ROS for robot control and communication with Isaac Sim from NVIDIA for visualization and simulation of physics, as can be seen in Fig. 1. Its modular and flexible architecture allows integration with various robot platforms, algorithms, and research objectives.

A. Key Features

- **Scene Randomization:** Dynamic placement of goals, obstacles, and robots.
- **Data Generation:** Real-time path planning, collision detection, robot status labels, and synthetic sensor streams.
- **Scalability:** Simulation of multiple robots in diverse industrial scenarios.
- **Platform:** Built with ROS and Isaac Sim for enhanced robot/algorithm compatibility.

B. Components

1) *Python-based Standalone Application:* Manages simulation workflows using the Isaac Sim Python API, handling scene setup, task assignments, and data logging. Customizable parameters enable tailored simulations, with a stopping condition for task completion or errors.

2) *Isaac Sim Interface:* Provides map generation, semantic labeling, and real-time data synchronization. The ROS interface enables dynamic map updates, sensor simulation, and autonomous navigation.

3) *ROS Integration:* Ensures compatibility with diverse robot platforms and sensors. Researchers can test algorithms for path planning, multi-agent coordination, and human-robot interaction in simulation before deployment on physical hardware.

4) *Scene Generation and Data Collection:* Generates randomized scenes reflecting real-world variability. Captures synthetic and performance data—including perception, trajectories, collisions, and environmental parameters—for machine learning and algorithm validation.

These features ensure scalability and adaptability, supporting research from robot behavior learning to large-scale industrial simulations.

III. ENABLING RESEARCH DOMAINS

A. Robot Learning

The pipeline provides a robust platform for robot learning by generating dynamic and diverse environments that simulate the complex, ever-changing conditions of industrial settings [4]. Through scene randomization, it creates varied obstacles, lighting conditions, and task assignments, enabling

Fig. 1. Architecture of the designed framework

the generation of high-quality synthetic data such as robot trajectories and sensor streams. This data is essential for training machine learning algorithms to enhance robot navigation, object detection, and decision-making. By replicating real-world variability, the pipeline helps develop adaptable models that can effectively navigate the dynamic environments found in modular production systems, where tasks and layouts change continuously.

B. Virtual Experimentation and Digital Twin

As a 3D-digital twin platform, the pipeline could allow for real-time synchronization between simulated and physical systems, creating an advanced environment for virtual experimentation [5]. In the context of flexible, modular production systems, this capability allows for the testing of robots in environments where production layouts and active elements (e.g., robots, human workers, production equipment) are dynamically changing. By simulating real-time task planning and robot actions in these evolving environments, the pipeline ensures that robots can optimize their behavior, making them ready for deployment in unpredictable real-world factory settings. Additionally, the pipeline facilitates virtual feasibility tests for tasks by enabling the testing of robot skills, such as object manipulation and navigation, in varied conditions before physical implementation. This allows for early validation of task execution strategies and skill effectiveness, reducing the risk of failure when transitioning to real-world environments.

C. Human-Robot Interaction, Collaboration, and Safety

The pipeline can enable realistic human-robot collaboration by simulating dynamic human behaviors, such as movement, task involvement, and even idle motions, allowing

robots to adapt and collaborate safely in real-time. It can go beyond static models by testing robots' responses to human actions in shared workspaces, optimizing workflows and ensuring safety. In addition, it simulates complex high-risk scenarios such as factory layout changes and system failures, helping to test and refine decision-making algorithms to ensure robots can navigate and respond safely to hazards before real-world deployment [6] [7].

IV. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE RESEARCH

This simulation pipeline addresses Industry 4.0 challenges by providing a scalable, adaptable environment for modular manufacturing, supporting system adaptation, learning, and validation. It fosters interdisciplinary research in symbolic learning, virtual experimentation, and flexible production design.

Future developments will improve digital twin synchronization and adaptive robot learning. Real-time data integration will refine algorithms and validate designs before deployment [8], creating a dynamic link between virtual and physical systems for realistic simulations.

Simulating large robot fleets enables research in swarm behavior, decentralized task allocation, and congestion management, enhancing coordination and collision avoidance [9]. AI-driven and context-sensitive robotics will further improve decision making by adapting to real-time inputs. This strengthens autonomous navigation and human-robot collaboration in complex, dynamic settings.

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